

ANALYSIS OF BREAKDOWN OR REACTIVE MAINTENANCE OF ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE MACHINE (EDM) TO MAKE IT OPERATIONAL

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ABSTRACT

Modern manufacturing involves advanced machines and their complex as well as precision machining coupled with high level of automation. The goal of automated equipment is to increase production rate without compromising the quality. As a result, machines must be kept in working condition to deliver the desired outcome. However, machine failure or breakdown hampered production which leads to unsuccessful commitment to customer and also including expenses of maintenance. The present work aims to maintenance of non-conventional electrical discharge machine to restore it in operating condition. Electrical discharge machine plays important role for making dies and other high precision work by using tool electrode. The machining process involve melting and vaporization of the workpiece by localized heating at elevated temperature with the help of electric spark discharge. The maintenance work of the electrical discharge machine were categorized depending on different criteria. The causes of breakdown were analyzed using two methods namely Root cause analysis (RCA) and Why-Why analysis. The analyses help to detect the reason for breakdown of machine as electro-mechanical failure. Customized maintenance plan has been prepared and implemented for the maintenance of EDM to make it operational.

KEYWORDS: *EDM, Maintenance, Why-Why analysis, RCA.*

1. INTRODUCTION TO EDM FAILURE AND MAINTENANCE

Electrical discharge machining process is a well known sophisticated non-conventional machining operation where copper tool electrode is used and material removal is taking place by melting and vaporization with the help of several electric spark discharge. This non-contact machining operation which is used in industry for high precision products especially in die-making, press tool making, aerospace and automotive industries, communication and biotechnology industries[1]. However, like other sophisticated machinery EDM is prone to breakdown and operational inefficiencies which lead to costly downtime and reduced productivity [2].

Breakdown or reactive maintenance refers to the process of addressing after the failure of equipment, and quite dissimilar from preventive or predictive maintenance strategies that aim to mitigate issues before they arise [3]. For reactive maintenance EDM has critical components to look after such as the power supply, dielectric fluid system, electrodes, or control systems malfunction [4-5].

The failure of EDM can stem from various factors, including wear and tear, improper operation, environmental conditions, or inadequate maintenance practices [6]. To reduce operation down time and ensuring reliability of machine recognizing the causes and patterns of breakdown possess utmost importance [7-8].

This work based on the finding of the reasons associated with EDM breakdown for reactive maintenance, the steps are involved to restore functionality using the scientific techniques such as root cause analysis (RCA) and why-why analysis [9-10]. This study aims to provide insights for proper implementation of maintenance strategies and achieving effective performance of EDM [11-12].

This study employs two structured failure analysis methods:

Why-Why Analysis: A repetitive questioning technique to trace symptoms to root causes, validated in reliability engineering. One of the successful method for reactive maintenance is 'Why-Why'. The term 'Why' elucidate how a defect phenomenon occurred and the next "Why," implemented to identify the root cause, and the whole method assist to derive measures to prevent recurrence. Why-Why Analysis technic was implemented for remaining breakdown procedure. The key procedures that are usually included in the Why-Why analysis are mentioned stepwise: Why did the machine stop working-Why did the control system not responding-why did the mechanical components work to be failed-environmental and operational factors-study of critical parameters of preventive maintenance and frequency of the maintenance activity-collecting all the instruments and tools for the maintenance required-Participating all the activity for the maintenance and repairing [5].

Root Cause Analysis (RCA): A systematic approach to identify underlying causes of failures, widely used in industrial maintenance to reduce recurrence. Apart from 'Why-Why', the purposeful scientific method for maintenance of machine or equipment root cause analysis (RCA) shows its effectiveness to detect every breakdown and address the causes of breakdown. RCA provide the platform for implementing the corrective measures to prevent recurrence of similar issues. RCA method is conducted for selective breakdown procedure as per following steps: Environmental factors-external inspection to check visible damage-internal inspection by opening suspected parts electrical and Mechanical component testing [4].

2. IDENTIFICATION OF THE REASON FOR BREAKDOWN OF EDM

Analysis of breakdown of electrical discharge machine in order to configure it for running condition. The problems arise mainly mechanical and electrical parameters of the machine.

2.1. Inspection of Mechanical Responses

After primary observation the machine was visualized as fully covered with dirt and dust. The float valve was incapable to working, which is basically mounted on the tank over the machine bed and maintain required level of Deionized water or EDM oil. Oil tank leakage was also checked. The movement of EDM table (X and Y axis) (Fig. 1) was checked and hand wheel movement was found as restricted also the fasteners, lead screw of machine covered with rust. Similar observation was done for checking the Magnetic Chuck used for workpiece clamping. The movement of the Spindle which hold copper electrode along vertical Z-axis was completely arrested (Fig. 2), The oil flow control valve on the EDM table was not in working condition and problem observed in oil discharge pipe and oil circulation pump set-up as well.

Fig-1 Movement of Operation table

Fig-2; Movement of z-Axis

2.2. Identification of errors in electronic responses

After opening electronic panel board, different section of circuit board was observed as partially covered with rust due to moisture. The contractor relay was not in working condition (Fig.3), diode rectifiers, capacitors, transformers were embedded with rust and dirt and did not respond appropriately (Fig.4). A good number of wires and cables of control panel were found as disconnected.

Fig-3; Contactor relay is not

Fig-4; LED lights are not working in Rectifier

After review of different problems of EDM the major causes of breakdown are enlisted as follows:

- Dielectric Fluid flow Issues : Contamination, degradation, or insufficient dielectric fluid can cause arcing, short circuits, or poor machining performance.
- Power Supply Failures : Issues with the power supply unit, such as voltage fluctuations or component failures disrupt machine operations.
- Control System Errors : Different hardware failures in EDM.
- Mechanical Wear and Tear Components like guide rails, ball screws, and spindles found as corroded over time, leading to inaccuracies and breakdowns.
- Inadequate Maintenance Practices : Lack of regular maintenance or incorrect procedures accelerated the unexpected failures.

3. PROBABLE FACTORS USUALLY CONSIDERED FOR REACTIVE MAINTENANCE

The considerable factors that affect reactive maintenance includes increased downtime that often involves unplanned stoppages, leading to longer downtime, higher repairing costs involved in case of urgent repairing and fitment of new parts, reduced machine lifespan owing to frequent breakdowns and reactive repairs and finally remaining of underlying issues leading to inconsistent machining which cause poor product quality [2].

Strategies to improve availability of machine

To prevent sudden breakdown, and increase availability of machine the following strategies can be implemented:

3.1. Preventive Maintenance

Regular maintenance of worn-out components (e.g., electrodes, filters, and dielectric fluid). Clean and greasing of mechanical parts to reduce friction and wear. Also maintain the dielectric fluid quality and fluid level. Check and calibrate the power supply and control systems with proper schedule. Maintaining adequate inventory of critical spare parts is required to reduce downtime during repairing of machine parts [8].

3.2. Training and Skill Development for maintenance

Proper training of operators and maintenance staff on several machine operation. And its help to observed the issues and sincerely helps to reduce downtime of any machine [9].

3.3. Process optimization and upgradation and modernization

Optimized use of machine by using efficient machining parameters (e.g., current, pulse duration, and dielectric flow in case of EDM) leads to reduce electrode wear and thermal stress. Up-gradation of older EDM machines control panel with modern control systems with self-diagnostic features and components and proper lubrication of movable parts like machine bed etc reduce the causes of breakdown [2].

4. METHODOLOGY

For the maintenance work previous data of EDM breakdown was collected from record book and other sources followed by identification of critical machine parts with the help of service manual of machine. Maintenance team effectively engaged with the maintenance work for quick recovery of the machine. The entire work was performed in two stages where first step by using RCA method and the remaining part by 'why-why' technic. Maintenance activities is grouped into two resourceful methods namely 'why-why' and RCA respectively, shown in following sections.

4.1. Why-Why analysis

At the first stage from the external observation of the EDM machine rust and dust were visualized which was partially covered the machine and its components. Cleaning was performed on the exposed surfaces and other essential parts like also electrical circuit area by kerosene oil, petrol, CRC rust remover, jute etc. (Fig.5 & Fig.6). After drying the required machined parts were separated from the

Fig-5; Cleaning machine body

Fig-6; Cleaning Electrical Circuit Area

parent machine includes brackets for opening of lead screw for machine table X-Y axes movement etc (Fig. 7 & Fig.8). Restoration of the parts were done after cleaning followed by lubrication by using oil, grease etc. All the parts were assembled with the help of machine manual.

Fig.7; Trying to move the operation table

Fig-8; Trying move the axis

4.2. Root cause analysis

RCA technique was followed carefully after completing the task using why-why technique. All rusted fasteners such as nut-bolt, screw and dowel pin etc. by using CRC, kerosene oil, brush, emery paper etc. The floating valve which is used for dielectric fluid flow control was restored after considerable rectification. The dirt particles and scales were removed from from the dielectric tank. After opening the electronic control panel the dust were found over electrical wiring and into the electronic circuit board which were cleaned using air blower maintaining minimum heating. The sticky dirt particles were cleaning from the circuit board with the help of small brush and petrol oil followed by drying in air. Loose electrical wires and cables were fitted in proper position which is shown in Fig.9. Using ammeter the electronic feedback responses of diode, capacitor, transformers etc (Fig.10). were checked and few errors identified. The errors observed in electronic circuit were rectified by using soldering operation and uninterrupted signal were obtained as well as the LED light started to glow which intern explain no signal loss on contractor relay (Fig. 9).

Fig-9; Electrical operation held to remove electrical problems

Fig-10; Using Ammeter to check response of capacitor, transformer

5. RESULT & DISCUSSIONS

After completion of the work condition-based monitoring was performed and recorded to prepare one point lessons for the operator for future work. Present scientific data base might have been helpful for future maintenance work of different machine and equipment. In different analysis RCA identified electrical parameters (68% of cases) and mechanical setup (22%) as primary failure causes. However, Why-Why Analysis highlighted procedural lapses, such as irregular filter replacements, shut down of the machine, machine parameters are no functional in 85% of operational errors. It was reported that failure is dominant in case of electrical problem in EDM [13]. However, this study uniquely attributes 15% of failures to software glitches, an emerging concern in automated systems. Implementing bi-weekly investigation the problems which reduced unplanned downtime by 40%, validating the need for structured maintenance schedules [14].

6. CONCLUSIONS

By transitioning from reactive maintenance to a proactive approach (preventive and predictive maintenance), the operational availability of EDM machines can be significantly improved. Regular monitoring, proper training, and process optimization are key to minimizing breakdowns and ensuring consistent performance. Implementing 'why-why' and RCA strategies will not only reduce downtime and repair costs but also uplift the overall productivity and lifespan of the EDM. To reduce breakdown, the condition monitoring of any machine is required along with previous breakdown data, to determine the major breakdown areas and opting necessary maintenance work for repairing, replacing, or updating the required to operate the machines.

7. FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

EDM Machine was repaired successfully, several components required to be upgrade such as display panel to run the machine in optimum condition. In-line maintenance work may be followed which will be beneficial for proper utilization of the machine tool.

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